

AN ASPECT OF HUMAN POTENTIAL AS A BASIS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICAL ORGANIZATION

Tulepbayeva G.

*Doctoral student of Business Administration
Almaty Management University*

Abstract

Considering the personnel policy as an integral part of the management activities and production policy of the organization, one can trace the relationship between the effective operation of the organization and the development of a market economy, the development of an innovative economy. Within the framework of this article, the human potential of the organization and its characteristics are considered. The relationship between human potential and the activities of the organization is revealed. The necessity of purposeful work in the management of human capital in the framework of achieving the strategic goals of the organization is substantiated.

Keywords: Human potential, human resource management, management of healthcare organization, human capital, people in healthcare management.

In modern conditions, the most successful is an organization that has highly professional staff, specialists focused on self-education, on the development of innovative activity, able to quickly respond to changes in internal and external conditions. This can be regarded as a necessary condition for an effective personnel policy and effective management of human potential.

An analysis of scientific sources has shown that the concept of human potential is considered as a certain set of skills and characteristics of personnel that directly affect the efficiency of the production process of an organization, its stability in the market of services provided (products). This explains the need to monitor the indicators of personnel potential, which allows to conduct an objective assessment of the potential of personnel and promptly develop and implement corrective measures to optimize the distribution of areas of responsibility and functional responsibilities between departments and employees of the organization. The rational use of human potential is directly related to the possibility of improving the quality characteristics of production, and, therefore, will ensure the competitiveness of the organization (Tursunbayeva, Di Lauro, Pagliari, 2018).

A personnel policy focused on the preservation and development of human potential will ensure an increase in the organization's profit indicators, the growth of its well-being, the creation of the necessary reserves necessary either to diversify the organization's activities or expand current production. Psychophysiological, socio-demographic, qualification and personal are considered as the main components of the employee's potential. Within these components, they consider: health, performance, endurance, abilities and inclinations of a person, age, gender, marital status, level of education, the amount of special knowledge, work skills, the ability to innovate, intelligence, creativity, professionalism, attitude to work, discipline, activity, value orientations, morality, etc (Morey et al., 2012). Thus, within the framework of personnel policy, it is necessary to pay close attention not only to the formation of human potential, but to its development, in accordance with the strategic plans of the organization, thereby forming strategic human capital, namely, forming such a set of employees who can be involved in the

production process if necessary and will be able to take part in the elimination of undesirable indicators of current activities due to the existing accumulated experience, due to the knowledge necessary to solve the problem (Renee Baptiste, 2017). Thus, dividing the human capital of the organization into current and strategic, while the current human potential is considered as allowing the organization to carry out effective activities at the current moment, and strategic, as focused on achieving the strategic goals of the organization.

In this regard, the question of effective management of the human potential of the organization arises. The market economy defines this process as a priority and dictates its own conditions for managing the human resources potential of an organization, including the assessment of human resources, the development of human resources, the creation of advanced training programs and the increase in the motivation of the workforce through the creation of incentive programs.

The priority areas that contribute to the development of elements of the human capital management process include:

- ongoing assessment of human capital;
- personalized, objective approach to assessing the achievements of employees in the framework of development programs;
- targeted approach to recruitment, based on indicators of human capital;
- development of an adequate system of employee motivation, integrated into the system of indicators of human capital that meets the requirements and the goals of the organization.

Thus, human capital management based on an effective personnel policy contributes to the development of an innovative climate, competitiveness and sustainability of the organization in the market of services provided (Tursunbayeva, Di Lauro, Pagliari, 2018).

Under the current conditions, healthcare is experiencing a shortage of personnel, but, on the other hand, the work of medical workers is increasingly becoming highly specialized, based on the possession of unique skills and knowledge that must be reproduced and updated. However, the functioning of the reproductive process and the development of the human potential of

health workers are currently complicated, which determines the importance and significance of the research topic. In general, potential is a set of any means and opportunities necessary to achieve a certain result (Jeffcott & MacKenzie, 2014).

Human potential is a complex characteristic of the level of development of intellectual, creative capabilities, resources of a country, industry, organization, individual. Even without a clear numerical expression, the human health potential, however, can be characterized by a number of basic qualitative characteristics.

The modern economy clearly demonstrates the fact that intellectual resources are increasingly involved in the sphere of market exchange. The competence of the head of a medical institution can no longer be limited to the field of purely medical knowledge, understanding the features of the functioning of the health care system or the specifics of medical activity. Today, he must possess professional knowledge and skills, intellectual abilities, which ensures innovative developments in the field of healthcare and the introduction of innovations. The imperative of maximizing material well-being was replaced by the awareness of the possibility of self-affirmation through the possession and ability to use knowledge.

Modern conditions require from the head of a high level of availability and constant development:

- professional knowledge;
- skills and abilities of practical guidance;
- personal potential;
- ability for professional development both in the field of medicine and in the field of management;
- communicative competence and level of language training.

The values of the organization can have a significant impact on the motivation of the interaction of employees, staff turnover and performance in general (Tursunbayeva, 2019).

Effective personnel management is almost always difficult if the enterprise does not have rules of conduct observed by all employees. A system of values that is unified and understandable to employees (the purpose and goals of the company, principles for carrying out

production activities, attitudes towards personnel, consumers and product quality) and adequate methods for their implementation (behavior of the managerial level, rules and norms of the organization, methods of interaction, system of work with personnel) creates an environment for effective work. The difficult socio-economic situation in the regions of Kazakhstan requires its speedy resolution through the implementation of economic reforms that have a full scientific and methodological justification.

In modern Kazakhstani medicine, it is necessary to change the minds of doctors, to develop an effective transparent incentive system for healthcare workers, which will eliminate informal payments for medical care and focus on achieving high performance, since such important indicators as the health of the population depend on the degree of motivation of medical workers for highly productive work in development and enhancement of the country's human potential.

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